

The Influence of TikTok Hosts on Customer Trust and Engagement in the Live Streaming Shop for Men's Grooming Products

Filipi Orlando¹, Ira Fachira²

¹ Research Student, School of Business and Management, Bandung Institute of Technology, Indonesia

² Assistant Professor, School of Business and Management, Bandung Institute of Technology, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: This study examines the factors that influence trust and customer engagement during live streaming shop sessions on TikTok, with a particular focus on men's grooming products. The study tested five variables, which are visual appearance, host approach (promotion and humor), interaction (review the product and consultation), trust in host, and customer engagement, with a survey of 319 respondents and analyzed with PLS-SEM method. The study found that visual appearance, host approach by promotion, and interaction with consultation have a positive relationship with trust in the host, while host approach by humor and interaction with review the products are rejected. Trust in the host has a positive relationship with customer engagement. The results provide insights for the hosts of men's grooming products on TikTok live streaming shops, highlighting the importance of visual appearance, promotion, and consultation in building trust with viewers. Humor should be used with caution, as they can negatively impact trust, and reviewing products is just a mandatory for host and could not build trust based on it. Lastly, the interaction through consultation is particularly effective in building trust. Thus, this trust factor is increasing, the customer engagement will build in the TikTok live streaming session.

KEYWORDS: Customer Engagement, Host Approach, Interaction, Men's Grooming Product, TikTok Live Streaming, Trust in Host, Visual Appearance.

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the biggest social media platforms today is TikTok with 689 million active users in 2023 [1]. In 2016, this application was first launched by ByteDance, a Chinese company [1]. The users are generally adolescents, about 52,83% aged between 18 to 24 years old [2], seeking entertainment or gathering information. People can access TikTok from a website (by computer) or smartphone. The user's main page posts will first see the so-called for-your-page (*fyp*). People often race to get their posts established on *fyp* posts because they will be seen by many TikTok users that have a similar preference for the *fyp* post. The live streaming shop feature is present on this platform. TikTok user can now sell their products on TikTok while promoting it altogether. There will be a host (or more) on TikTok's live shop broadcast that will accompany the viewers. The host would explain the product, persuade them to buy it and entertain the viewers to create purchasing intention. The most popular social media site in Indonesia is TikTok with 69% of Indonesian use the platform [3].

Men's grooming products have evolved significantly in recent years, providing various options to suit every need. Sales of men's grooming products have been growing at a faster rate than those of women's grooming products since 2010 [4]. This growth was driven by the increasing number of men who are becoming more conscious of their appearance and investing in skincare products. Based on Indonesia, some skincare brands have been made exclusively for men, such as Kahf and Cloris Men, but there are some other companies sell various brands, like Gamal-Men do. Furthermore, there is men segmentation brand that comes from women beauty product producers, it is Erha with his men segmentation brands, His Erha. As men's grooming products have grown in popularity, and TikTok Live Shop offers the advantageous stage for exhibiting these products. On the use of live shopping, companies can quickly transform their TikTok shopping experiences into live sessions. Building relationships with host's audience and fostering brand awareness can both be accomplished by being responsive and engaged as live streaming is going on in TikTok live streaming. TikTok often give many benefits when customers want to buy the product at a live session shop. Free shipping is applied for people that purchase in the live TikTok in certain location.

Business Issue

Even though with the high potential market for company that want to use TikTok live streaming platform, there is some issues present. As survey toward viewer and sold items on Kaft, His Erha, Gamal-Men, and Cloris Men brand, it is found some of their live streaming viewers is low compared other as shown on the **Table 1**. It shows that one brand of men's grooming shop even has average audience below 20 people on TikTok live shop. Kahf tends to have more views than the three other brands. Although Gamal Men went live longer than Kahf, it didn't generate more viewers than Kahf. According to Keutelian on a global scale [5], the highest engagement was on the day until the afternoon on the weekday. Still, on the weekend, the engagement of audience watching the live streaming still tends to be lower. Rooting the possibility of causes, there are various factors that could affect the low engagement of live streaming for men's grooming product on TikTok. One of factors that must be focused on is the host, because they will be the center of attention of the event, and their persuasion power will affect the customer engagement. However, there is still lack of knowledge on host, especially on men's grooming product, which has potential market with TikTok platform. Thus, this research is conducted to analyze factors that are came from the host with the objective based on previous research and internet knowledge on how to be a good host. Example of low on viewers on TikTok live streaming is shown in **Figure 1**.

Table 1. Data viewers of live sessions of brand accounts on TikTok live shop

Day	Date*	Time	Kahf	His Erha	Gamal Men	Cloris Men
Thursday	23/02/23	08.16	OFF	4	OFF	5
Thursday	23/02/23	09.20	OFF	5	OFF	OFF
Thursday	23/02/23	10.27	10	Other/OFF**	OFF	OFF
Thursday	23/02/23	15.52	OFF	Other/OFF**	9	OFF
Thursday	23/02/23	15.53	OFF	Other/OFF**	11	12
Thursday	23/02/23	16.55	OFF	Other/OFF**	OFF	11
Thursday	23/02/23	18.55	OFF	Other/OFF**	9	21
Thursday	23/02/23	20.00	102	Other/OFF**	19	OFF
Friday	24/02/23	07.31	50	26	2	1
Friday	24/02/23	07.32	41	Other/OFF**	2	1
Friday	24/02/23	14.43	29	Other/OFF**	OFF	11
Friday	24/02/23	15.53	111	Other/OFF**	OFF	8
Friday	24/02/23	16.50	106	Other/OFF**	12	15
Friday	24/02/23	23.07	OFF	Other/OFF**	3	OFF
Saturday	25/02/23	00.17	OFF	Other/OFF**	6	OFF
Saturday	25/02/23	07.50	OFF	Other/OFF**	OFF	23
Saturday	25/02/23	09.13	67	Other/OFF**	OFF	15
Saturday	25/02/23	11.59	46	Other/OFF**	7	12
Saturday	25/02/23	12.38	52	Other/OFF**	5	OFF
Saturday	25/02/23	12.39	45	Other/OFF**	7	OFF
Saturday	25/02/23	12.50	56	Other/OFF**	12	OFF
Saturday	25/02/23	14.05	36	Other/OFF**	7	18
Saturday	25/02/23	20.07	106	Other/OFF**	14	43
Saturday	25/02/23	21.28	OFF	Other/OFF**	12	97
Saturday	25/02/23	22.43	OFF	OFF	7	41
Sunday	26/02/23	00.40	OFF	OFF	OFF	OFF
Sunday	26/02/23	08.00	OFF	OFF	OFF	OFF

* using date format: dd/mm/yy

** Other: Live streaming session of other brand by its parent company

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Consumer Behavior

Consumer behavior research helps businesses understand customer decision-making processes and preferences, enabling them to develop effective marketing strategies and improve customer satisfaction and loyalty. Perception research is a critical aspect of marketing, as understanding how target audiences perceive products and messages can help create effective campaigns.

Figure 1. Some of live streaming shops have low viewers on TikTok live streaming.

Source: Screenshots of live streaming on TikTok in real-time by Author, 2023

Marketers use perception to grab people's attention and make their products memorable, as people tend to pay more attention to larger, noisier, or more colorful stimuli. Short-term memory is used to process and retain information for immediate tasks, while long-term memory is a more persistent form of memory storage that retains important or meaningful information for days, weeks, or a lifetime. Explicit or declarative memory involves conscious recall, while implicit or non-declarative memory involves automatic processing of skills and habits.

Encoding information from short-term to long-term memory entails a complex set of cognitive and neurological processes, such as attention, perception, rehearsal/re-comprehend, and elaboration, shown in Figure 2. It is more likely that information that is reiterated or elaborated upon will be stored in long-term memory. Host of TikTok live streaming shop must maximize the stimuli of sound and visual, such as interesting or entertaining topic, catchy statement, attractive discussion, attractive visual color [6], showing some certain things from shop that could gather people, like big and colorful discount image in their live streaming.

Figure 2. Atkinson-Shiffrin model of memory

Visual Appearance

Visualization in live streaming has a significant effect on trust [7]. Thus, the placement of products and visual of host itself will be matter in the live streaming. In order to preserve a professional look, several streaming services have policies that forbid sexually explicit material or offer clothing rules for its hosts, thus in this research the visual is represent as masculine and feminine. Nonetheless, there are also circumstances when these traits may draw more viewers or help the presenter project a specific image, potentially boosting their popularity. There is study that finds feminine faces is more trustworthy than masculine one [8]. The findings of Zhao and Bacao research during Covid-19 pandemic that their study support the notion that gender significantly modifies impact expectancies, hedonic motivation, trust, social influence, and perceived worth [9].

It used to be that being considered beautiful meant possessing particular physical traits, like a nice face and a thin physique [10]. Viewers' perceptions of social reality can be significantly impacted by exposure to a specific set of values, particular individuals, and concepts in the media. According to Alboqami study [11], the physical aspect of the influencer had a significant impact on the consumers' trust in the AI influence. This finding suggests that physical beauty of an influencer in social media can aid in gaining and maintaining audience trust over time [11]. Hence, the hypothesis of host visual appearance will be put in this research that can affect the trust in host.

H1. The visual appearance of host on TikTok live streaming shop has a positive relationship with trust in host for men's grooming products.

Host Approach

Host in live streaming will be the center of attention in their events and the host ensures that the visitors or audience feel appreciated, welcomed, and invited by the minute customers step inside the business, as in the TikTok when they enter that session. The host should build a friendly and welcoming atmosphere [12].

Shop on TikTok often offered vouchers when viewers watched them live on a certain time, which provide audience interest to keep watch the streaming. Not only adult people, but teenagers also already using it and if they find the right brands for their skin, they don't hesitate to spend much money for it [13]. This determines whether discounts on skin care brands can convince consumers to switch from the brand they use to other brands that are discounted. Some shop sells products as bundle, because to have a good skin, people often need various types of skincare that have different functions and should applied sequentially. Buying bundle items usually can make the total price lower rather than buying individually as author saw on TikTok shop, such as brand Kaft, Clorismen, and Gaman Men. Promotion has positive significantly impact on increasing customer satisfaction and loyalty [14]. According to Suwaryu and Taufiqurahman's study of the Lazada Marketplace [15], a significant correlation was found between sales promotion and trust. Humor is a potent tool for engaging audiences and establishing relationships with consumers on TikTok Live Streaming Shop. Adding a touch of humor to a live streaming can make it more pleasurable and memorable for viewers, leading to increased engagement and sales. Humor and demonstration of product can be combined and with right composition will make the streaming more engaging. With various humour style in these days, some jokes could be effective to gain people interest [16]. The research of humor from Barta et al is found out that humor has important role for pursuing the TikTok users to follow their account [17]. The ability to utilize humor effectively as a leader may have a positive effect on many areas, including morale, productivity, teamwork, and the overall culture of a company.

- H2A.** The promotion approach of host on TikTok live streaming shop has a positive relationship with trust in host for men's grooming products.
- H2B.** The humor approach of host on TikTok live streaming shop has a positive relationship with trust in host for men's grooming products.

Interaction

TikTok allows for real-time interaction with their audience via social media. This includes responding to messages and comments, hosting live events, and offering prizes and competitions. Developing relationships with the host's audience and promoting brand awareness can be achieved by being responsive and active during live broadcasting. Therefore, the presenter must actively interact with the audience and discuss the products.

Products that are being sold on TikTok live shop can be a good method to conveyed product knowledge and value of the themselves. However, since people only can see it from screen, there are limit for viewer to observe the product, and it makes trust is one of the factors that viewers' need to build customer engagement [18]. Live streaming product reviews are recognized for authenticity and relatability. Hosts may show the product, explain its features, and share personal experiences, unlike written ads. This honest style makes viewers trust the presenter, which boosts credibility and impact. It is significantly more influential for the consumers rather than just reading the reviews from unknown buyers [19].

Interaction between consumer and seller has positive relation with the trust and consumer satisfaction [20]. Interaction such keep asking and answering from two people could create bonding, which in this case streamer and the viewer [18]. Some brand also has plenty alternative products with people that have different need, and the host can recommend based on the audience preferences. It will gain trust the customers by providing the details by consulting them.

- H3A.** Doing Review of Products of host on TikTok live streaming shop has a positive relationship with trust in host for men's grooming products
- H3B.** Doing Consultation of host on TikTok live streaming shop has a positive relationship with trust in host for men's grooming products

Trust in Host

Establishing and maintaining client trust is a crucial component of any business strategy and it plays a crucial role in boosting customer loyalty, positive customer evaluations and testimonials, and ultimately, revenue. Based on Hajli study, customers engage in these behaviors through using social commerce frameworks (rating and reviews, recommendation, and community forum) which boosts both trust and intent to purchase [21]. This trust in host is needed to construct customer engagement, which the variable that will be measure in this study. According to studies, there are revealed that live streaming purchasing behavior, as one of result of customer engagement, is positively correlated with entertainment, expertise, knowledge, and credibility build from trust [22], which are factors influence purchase intentions [23]. Per Amalia [18] and Wongkitrungrueng [24] researches, customer engagement is derived from trust in seller. Thus, the increasing trust in host is important variable, that can bridge the customer engagement with the independent variables.

- H4.** Trust in host on TikTok live streaming shop has a positive relationship with customer engagement for men's grooming products

Customer Engagement

The live streaming can be a good tool of direct selling with capacity on increasing customer engagement [24] and construct interaction. This interaction can be bridged between seller or host that explained about its value of products toward the customers. It encompasses the ongoing interactions between the seller and customers, serving as a clear indication of their active interest and involvement. Understanding the significance of these interactions allows businesses to foster stronger relationships, enhance customer loyalty, and drive long-term success [25]. The initial engagement is important as it represents an opportunity to make a positive impression, spark curiosity, and ignite the desire to explore further by the trust with the host.

Table 2. The previous research on constructing the hypothesis path

Code	Hypothesis Path	References
H1	Visual Appearance → Trust in Host	[11] [26] [9]
H2A	Host Approach (Promotion) → Trust in Host	[15] [14]
H2B	Host Approach (Humor) → Trust in Host	[17] [27] [20]
H3A	Interaction (Review the Products) → Trust in Host	[18] [28]
H3B	Interaction (Consultation) → Trust in Host	[18] [20]
H4	Trust in Host → Customer Engagement	[18] [7] [22] [24]

Figure 3. Conceptual Framework

3. METHODOLOGY

In this study, it is used the questionnaire method as a tool to collect data from respondents. A questionnaire is a research instrument consisting of a list of questions and an assortment of responses, written or typed in a particular order on a form used to collect specific information from respondents [29]. The conducted questionnaire will be shared Online through e-mail and some social media platforms, such as WhatsApp and Instagram. Whilst, a sample is a part of population from people that will be studied in this research. As a result, the number of the sample is smaller than the entire population, and the sample will be regarded as representative of the entire population. The questionnaire is intended for people who ever bought men's grooming product in live streaming shop on TikTok and people who intend to. In create a survey through a questionnaire, the measurement techniques that can be applied is Likert scale. This scale can specifically rate the opinion of respondent levels based on their own satisfaction, thus feedback from respondent can be comprehended into data that solving the objectives research [30]. The Likert 5-point scale shows the scale from Strongly Agree into Strongly Disagree according to the statements that will be given in the questionnaire. %. This survey was used pilot test to acquire the validity and reliability of the questions with SPSS using 30 samples. Then, the total survey processed with PLS-SEM method using SmartPLS.

The men's of grooming products are not limited buy one gender consumer – not just male. However, female can purchase it too, because there are many possibilities on why female buys men's grooming products, such as to give it to their own couple or a gift to others. Other reason, female is dominating the population of Online users on TikTok [31]. Thus, author conduct the survey toward female too. The result from the survey shows female respondent has larger than male with a slight difference 47,3% and 52,7% respectively, hence the data shows, female has interest on purchasing men's grooming products too. It happens because number of TikTok users of female is larger compared to male as in 2021 [32]. The largest of spending time in social media, including TikTok, is coming from adolescents – 18 to 24 years old [2]. People with those age are generally student and some are entry level of workers.

It is similar with the result of the survey that indicate most of the people are students and following by employees. based on previous research and literature review indicator [18], minimum size for problem-solving study is 200 samples [24], while typical good number of sample size is 300 – 500, which is, author conducts the research with 334 respondents. Total of sample is 319 respondents and the survey conducted in Indonesia. The respondents mostly are student 74,3% (237 respondents), with 300 respondents based on Western Indonesia Time (WIB), and 81,5% of respondents are 18 – 26 years old (Gen Z). Majority of them have experience of watching men's grooming product on TikTok live streaming 91,2%.

This research will analyze the sample habit, descriptive analysis, validity and reliability, discriminant validity, and coefficient determination. Thus, the last is hypothesis testing and discussion. After acknowledge the result, business solution for host on TikTok live streaming shop for men's grooming product will be discussed.

4. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive analysis is used for calculating the average of variable value based on respondents that answer the statements from questionnaire. The results will be gathered from PLS-SEM calculation, and from there, every variable that stated in from conceptual framework will be analyzed and elaborated in accordance of score from questionnaire. The level of score is parted from the mean value, which based on previous research [18], the score divided as: very low; low; medium; high; and very high, with the score range 1.00 – 1.80; 1.81 – 2.60; 2.61 – 3.20; 3.21 – 4.20; and 4.21 – 5.00 respectively. The score of each attribute of variable can be found in **Table 3**. The assessment from the survey is found that the mean of each of items are on high interpretation, but with one item is considered medium, which is CE2. However, based on the overall items of every variables result the show that the interpretation is high.

Validity and Reliability Test

The quality and trustworthiness of research results may be evaluated by looking at two key components of research methodology: validity and reliability. Validity determines whether or not the study's chosen research instrument or tool is adequate for assessing the variables of interest. Meanwhile, the term of reliability is used to describe how consistent, stable, and repeatable a study's results or measurements are. It determines whether or not the same findings are obtained whether the research instrument is used more than once or by various researchers.

The result of the survey will be tested by SmartPLS for validity and reliability on each attribute item. This section will be explained the data analysis result by its PLS Algorithm. The indicators from PLS algorithm calculation are Loading Factors, Cronbach's Alpha, A.V.E. (Average Variance Extracted), and C.R. (Composite Reliability). Loadings Factor and A.V.E. are used for measuring validity. On the other hand, Cronbach's Alpha and C.R. are used for measuring the reliability.

Factor loading in validity test indicates the proportion of variance explained by a variable on a specific factor. In the SEM method, a factor loading of 0.7 or higher indicates that the factor effectively extracts variance from the variable [33]. The algorithm verifies that each variable satisfies the outer loading value requirement. Another validity indicator is A.V.E, which based on previous study the minimum value is equal 0,5 or bigger to be considered valid [18]. The result shows each item of loading factors is above 0,7 and A.V.E. value of every variable is bigger than 0,5. It means the validity test of the survey result is valid. Based on the result of validity result, all Loadings factor and AVE are above its minimum value to be considered valid.

In Reliability Test, Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability is could be used one another or both, on which the theory or facts fit better. Both of value in order to be acceptable as reliable data should above 0,7 [34]. This reliability test found out that all Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability are higher than 0,7 which is reliable. This result is pass and considered valid and reliable data, and appropriate to study for certain purpose. The convergent validity and reliability test from the survey data can be seen on **Table 3**. Cronbach's alphas above 0.70 are considered good, 0.80 are considered excellent, and 0.90 are considered best [35].The value that is gathered from SmartPLS of reliability test are showing above 0,8 which considered excellent, but one variable, Trust in Host generate 0,799.

Discriminant Validity and Coefficient of Determination

Discriminant validity assesses whether or not theoretically unrelated constructs are actually unrelated [36]. Discriminant validity is crucial because it reveals whether the test accurately targets the construct of interest or assesses unintentionally related but distinct

constructs. This test conducted with the result on the **Table 4**. With the value on the diagonal cell should be bigger than the value of number below. It is showing all variable not related on each other relation which make their score on each other variable lower than itself score. Which this discriminant validity model is valid.

The following evaluation will be based on the R Square method of determining the coefficient. It is referring to the regression model, which measures how well independent variables can be predicted using the dependent variable [18]. Customer Engagement was found to be formed for 43,4% by Trust in Host, and Trust in Host was found to be constructed from Visual Appearance, Host Approach (Promotion and Humor), and Interaction (Review the Product and Consultation) with the value of 59,2%. These findings are based on the result of the R square statistic. Above 0,1 is the bare minimum required for a R square value in studies pertaining to the social sciences [37]. However, a score between 0,3 and 0,59 is regarded to be moderate [38].

Table 3. Assessment on conceptual framework

	Mean	Loadings	AVE	Cronbach's alpha	Composite Reliability
Customer Engagement					
CE1	3,32	0,771	0,571	0,875	0,903
CE2	3,20*	0,754			
CE3	3,34	0,703			
CE4	3,61	0,771			
CE5	3,33	0,805			
CE6	3,51	0,737			
CE7	3,48	0,744			
Trust in Host					
TH1	3,54	0,873	0,714	0,799**	0,882
TH2	3,48	0,869			
TH3	3,52	0,790			
Visual Appearance					
VA1	3,60	0,710	0,653	0,820	0,882
VA2	3,40	0,798			
VA3	3,63	0,847			
VA4	3,32	0,869			
Promotion					
HAP1	3,84	0,846	0,744	0,828	0,897
HAP2	3,74	0,872			
HAP3	3,76	0,868			
Humor					
HAH1	3,92	0,885	0,757	0,840	0,903
HAH2	3,94	0,876			
HAH3	3,66	0,849			
Review the product					
INR1	3,76	0,849	0,748	0,887	0,922
INR2	3,70	0,886			
INR3	3,65	0,877			

INR4	3,72	0,845			
Consultation					
INC1	3,69	0,888	0,765	0,846	0,907
INC2	3,70	0,857			
INC3	3,69	0,878			

* $2.61 \leq p \leq 3.20$

** $0,7 < p < 0,8$

Table 4. Discriminant Validity Result

	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7
F1 Consultation	0,756						
F2 Customer Engagement	0,659	0,845					
F3 Humor	0,648	0,581	0,808				
F4 Promotion	0,635	0,681	0,552	0,862			
F5 Review the Product	0,525	0,613	0,518	0,692	0,870		
F6 Trust in Host	0,622	0,679	0,609	0,743	0,641	0,865	
F7 Visual Appearance	0,588	0,691	0,573	0,697	0,661	0,775	0,874

Note: On the main diagonal, the square root of the AVE of each multi-item build is displayed in bold.

Hypothesis Testing

Each of hypothesis will be tested with the result as measured on **Table 5** below. The calculation done by SmartPLS with Bootstrapping calculation. The indicators on this testing are Original Sample or coefficient path, T-Statistics, and P-Value. Original Sample score shows the contribution of the path with the relationship on its dependent variable. It needs to be positive value in order to be contributed toward its dependent variable. T-Statistic score minimum is 1,96 to be considered significant [39], which mean there is effect on the hypothesis between independent and dependent variable. Another measurement is coming from P-Value, with the significant value on below 0,05. It is caused by the level significant that is used from the calculation is 95%. Hypothesis with P-Value more than 0,05 will be rejected.

Table 5. Hypothesis Test Result

HYPOTHESIS		ORIGINAL SAMPLE	T-STATISTICS	P-VALUE	RESULT
Visual Appearance → Trust in Host	(H1)	0,167	3,115	0,002	Accepted
Promotion → Trust in Host	(H2A)	0,236	3,470	0,001	Accepted
Humor → Trust in Host	(H2B)	0,109	1,748*	0,081**	Rejected
Review the product → Trust in Host	(H3A)	0,134	1,950*	0,052**	Rejected
Consultation → Trust in Host	(H3B)	0,256	3,221	0,001	Accepted
Trust in Host → Customer Engagement	(H4)	0,659	15,104	0,000	Accepted

* $p < 1,96$

** $p > 0,05$

Business Solution

The issues that have been stated in the previous chapters are the lack of knowledge of host factors influencing on increasing customer engagement on TikTok live streaming for men’s grooming product, which can lead into generating small sales, because of not

utilized the benefit from TikTok live streaming feature, while TikTok platform itself is one of the largest s-commerce platforms at this time [1], with a hundred millions of Indonesian become TikTok users [40].

- **Visual Appearance**
Visual appearance of the host that will represent the product and the company itself, the beauty of the host will be judged by the audience. The host will be the center of attention in the live streaming. The visual of host can be look as visual masculine or feminine, it also depends on the product or brand which some of them have specific kind of target market (ex. Beard product and skincare for flawless skin). Men's grooming product host on TikTok live streaming should be attractive, it will make the audience interested and more attracted toward the live streaming session. Host for men's grooming product should be well-groomed, thus it will represent as professionalism. The host will be the representative of the product, then host physical traits must be according with the products that they sell, hence the potent of the product will be well-resembled. Such as, product for younger generation could use host that comes from that segmentation too. Based on the survey, the visual masculine and feminine will influence the interest of audience too, but it still in accordance with people preference with certain of product.
- **Host Approach by telling Promotion**
Promotion is one of biggest factors for people to have purchase intention, as the price in the beauty industry is quite competitive. This promotion could be told with alternative product, a bundle product, or even new product that host can told toward the viewer. The host must well-understand the product. Including its promotion, such as all discounted items or any bundle that usually have bigger price in normal circumstance. The host can survey on the other platforms of any products for finding the comparison of price. In the live streaming session, host can keep telling the promotion they have, even when there is no one asked about it, and host must focus on the comment section if in case, there is a question asked about the product that you aware that it have the cheaper alternative product or such.
- **Interaction as consultation**
This interaction is more than one question and answer between the host and viewer. The consultation is interaction in order to gain other information of the audience, thus the host can give more accurate recommendation about the product that is suitable for them. The host should keep asking the viewer preferences after initial question, they usually ask the host to review the product that viewer interest for. Put more sympathetic toward their struggle on why they need to purchase some certain of product. This will make more persuasion value, because they will feel cared by the host. The host need understand of various kind of typical people skin, since there are many products of men's grooming that have specialty toward certain condition and traits of people.

5. CONCLUSION

The advanced technology as nowadays helps people to do things more practically in many ways. Such as shopping at anywhere and it can be used easily by people. S-commerce like TikTok is one of platforms that joining social media with e-commerce and offers many features. The conclusion based on the research that is conducted, the visual appearance, promotion approach, and consultation with viewers are crucial in building trust and engagement in a TikTok live streaming shop of men's grooming products. A well-groomed, professional, and relatable visual appearance of the host can establish a connection and build trust among viewers. Demonstrating product knowledge and expertise through the promotion approach can establish credibility and showcase understanding of the products being promoted. Active interaction and personalized consultation with viewers during the live streaming session can create a sense of inclusivity and connection, leading to more trust and engagement. However, humor approach and review of products are not supported variables in building trust in the host.

Practical Implication

This study provide some practical insight that can be seen as follows. First, the hosts of TikTok shop that sells men's grooming product should ensure they present themselves in a professional and relatable manner. This includes grooming well, dressing appropriately, and aligning their appearance with the target audience. Investing in personal grooming and maintaining a visually appealing presence can help build trust and resonate with viewers. Next, the hosts also should strive to be knowledgeable about the men's grooming products they are promoting. This includes staying updated on the latest trends, understanding the benefits and features of the products, and sharing genuine experiences and testimonials. Then, encourage active participation from viewers by

soliciting their opinions, questions, and feedback during live streaming sessions. Respond promptly and genuinely to viewer comments, addressing their concerns and providing personalized recommendations. Building a consultative environment fosters engagement and establishes a sense of trust and collaboration. Consistently uphold professionalism and integrity in all interactions and promotions. Avoid using excessive or inappropriate humor that may be misinterpreted or offend viewers. Ensure that the focus remains on providing valuable information and guidance to viewers, reinforcing the perception of credibility and trustworthiness.

Limitation

Based on industry background and business challenges, the analysis scope defines this research's bounds to meet its goals. Due to unresolved commercial concerns, social media/e-commerce platform TikTok will lead. TikTok store has numerous unique features, including a live streaming shop that some influencers have used to increase sales. Indonesia's geography also limited the events. Because each nation's culture shapes everyday behaviors. Men's grooming products are trending more than ever, exceeding women's growth internationally. Thus, the product's constraint will be TikTok, one of the largest social media and e-commerce platforms, where many firms will target men's grooming product customers. The stores to be taught are confined to legitimate TikTok accounts and sell locally. If the customer and seller are from different countries, TikTok will not act as a third-party intermediary to sell things. This research examined TikTok events and observations from January 2023 to May 2023.

Future Research Suggestion

The future research suggestions are considered as follows. First, deeply examine the role of host personality traits in building trust and/or engagement of customer. Investigate whether certain personality traits, such as confidence, humor, or relatability, have a stronger impact on viewer engagement and trust. The second suggestion is assessing the effectiveness of different product demonstration techniques in promoting trust and engagement. These studies can provide valuable guidance to hosts, sellers, and platform developers in optimizing their strategies for enhanced customer trust, engagement, and business success.

REFERENCES

1. Karl. (2023). The 15 Biggest Social Media Sites and Apps [2023]. Retrieved from <https://www.dreamgrow.com/top-15-most-popular-social-networking-sites/>
2. Ceci, L. (2022, October 18). TikTok - Statistics & Facts. Retrieved from Statista: https://www.statista.com/topics/6077/tiktok/#topicHeader__wrapper
3. Nurhayati-Wolff, H. (2022). Leading social media platforms to watch live shopping Indonesia 2022. Retrieved from <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1347400/indonesia-leading-social-media-platforms-to-watch-live-shopping/?locale=en>
4. Ballard, B. (2019). A solid business foundation – male make-up enters the boardroom. Retrieved 2023, from <https://www.europeanceo.com/lifestyle/a-solid-business-foundation-male-make-up-enters-the-boardroom/>
5. Keutelian, M. (2022). The best times to post on social media in 2022. Retrieved February 25, 2023, from <https://sproutsocial.com/insights/best-times-to-post-on-social-media/>
6. Purwanegara, M. S. (2022). Consumer Perception. Bandung: Institut Teknologi Bandung.
7. Ma, L., Gao, S., & Zhang, X. (2022). How to Use Live Streaming to Improve Consumer Purchase Intentions: Evidence from China. Retrieved from doi.org/10.3390/su14021045
8. Costello, W. (2023). Face Value: The importance of feminine mystique in perceived facial trustworthiness. Retrieved from <https://williamcostello.medium.com/face-value-the-importance-of-feminine-mystique-in-perceived-facial-trustworthiness-f3b5680f02d2>
9. Zhao, Y., & Bacao, F. (2021). How Does Gender Moderate Customer Intention of Shopping via Live-Streaming Apps during the COVID-19 Pandemic Lockdown Period? Retrieved from doi.org/10.3390/ijerph182413004
10. Chua, T. H., & Chang, L. (2015). Follow me and like my beautiful selfies: Singapore teenage girls' engagement in self-presentation and peer comparison on social media. Retrieved from dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2015.09.011
11. Alboqami, H. (2023). Trust me, I'm an influencer! - Causal recipes for customer trust in artificial intelligence influencers in the retail industry. Retrieved from doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2022.103242
12. Resources. (2023). Host or Hostess job description. Retrieved from <https://resources.workable.com/host-or-hostess-job-description>

13. Pattyranie, A. (2019). Demi Jaga Kulit dengan Menggunakan Skincare, Intan Rela Merogoh Kocek hingga Rp 500 Ribu per Bulan. Retrieved from <https://manado.tribunnews.com/2019/08/29/demi-jaga-kulit-dengan-menggunakan-skincare-intan-rela-merogoh-kocek-hingga-rp-500-ribu-per-bulan>
14. Widodo, A., & Murwatingsih. (2019). The Influence of Promotion and Trust on Customer Loyalty through Customer Satisfaction. *Management Analysis Journal*, 3, 265-274.
15. Suwaryu, L., & Taufiqurahman, E. (2022). The Effect of Sales Promotion and Trust on Purchase Decisions on the Lazada Marketplace. *JURNAL EKONOMI DAN BISNIS*, 20(3), 1-12.
16. Thomson, J. (2022). Why do some people love cringe comedy while others can't stand it? Retrieved from <https://bigthink.com/high-culture/cringe-comedy/>
17. Barta, S., Belanche, D., Fernandez, A., & Marta, F. (2022). Influencer marketing on TikTok: The effectiveness of humor and followers' hedonic experience. Retrieved from doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2022.103149
18. Amalia, R. A. (2022). Factors Influencing Customer Engagement on Live Streaming Social Commerce. Bandung: Institut Teknologi Bandung.
19. Chen, H., Dou, Y., & Xiao, Y. (2022). Understanding the Role of Live Streamers in Live-Streaming E-Commerce. Retrieved from <https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4141864>
20. Hou, F., Guan, Z., Li, B. C., & Loong, A. Y. (2019). Factors Influencing People's Continuous Watching Intention and Consumption Intention in Live Streaming: Evidence from China. China: University of Nottingham.
21. Hajli, N. (2015). Social commerce constructs and consumer's intention to buy. Retrieved from dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2014.12.005
22. Sarah, & Sobari, N. (2022). THE EFFECT OF LIVE STREAMING ON PURCHASE INTENTION OF E-COMMERCE CUSTOMERS. The 6th International Conference on Family Business and Entrepreneurship, 6th, 282-290.
23. Sawmong, S. (2022). Examining the Key Factors that Drives Live Stream Shopping Behavior. *Emerging Science Journal*, 6(6), 1394-1408.
24. Wongkitrungrueng, A., & Assarut, N. (2020, September). The role of live streaming in building consumer trust and engagement with social commerce sellers. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2018.08.032>
25. Paton, J. (2022). What is customer engagement and why is it important? Retrieved May 17, 2023, from <https://dotdigital.com/blog/what-is-customer-engagement-and-why-is-it-important/>
26. Ledesma, A., Kraut, D., Quezada, R., Zayas, A., & Cano-Ruiz, M. E. (2020). Physical appearance and its effect on trust. *Emerging Investigators*, II, 1-6.
27. Harman, B. M. (2019). Using Laughter To Build Trust At Work. Retrieved from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/forbescoachescouncil/2019/04/10/using-laughter-to-build-trust-at-work/?sh=3bacd6ac43c9>
28. Chan, I. C., Chen, Z., & Leung, D. (2023, January 3). The more the better? Strategizing visual elements in social media marketin. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhtm.2022.11.007>
29. Aryal, S. (2022). Questionnaire method of data collection. Retrieved May 12, 2023, from <https://thebiologynotes.com/questionnaire-method-of-data-collection>
30. Jotform. (2023). How to create and analyze 5-point Likert scales. Retrieved May 12, 2023, from <https://www.jotform.com/blog/5-point-likert-scale/>
31. Statista. (2023). Number of TikTok accounts in Indonesia in 2022, by gender. Retrieved from <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1377390/indonesia-number-of-tiktok-accounts-by-gender/>
32. Angelia, D. (2022). Rajai Jumlah Unduhan Terbanyak, Bagaimana Statistik TikTok? Retrieved from <https://goodstats.id/article/rajai-jumlah-unduh-terbanyak-bagaimana-statistik-tiktok-ASDfx>
33. Statistics Solutions. (2023). Factor Analysis. (Statistic Solution) Retrieved from <https://www.statisticssolutions.com/free-resources/directory-of-statistical-analyses/factor-analysis/>
34. Hamid, M. R., W, S., & Sidek, M. H. (2017). Discriminant Validity Assessment: Use of Fornell & Larcker criterion versus HTMT Criterion. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*(890).
35. Statistics solution. (2023). Cronbach's Alpha. Retrieved from <https://www.statisticssolutions.com/cronbachs-alpha/>

36. Nikolopoulou, K. (2022). What Is Discriminant Validity? | Definition & Example. Retrieved from <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/discriminant-validity/>

37. Ozili, P. K. (2023). The acceptable R-square in empirical modelling for social science research. Munich: Munich Personal RePEc Archive.

38. Wilson, L. T. (2009). Statistical Correlation. Retrieved from <https://explorable.com/statistical-correlation>

39. Ghozali, I. (2018). Aplikasi analisis multivariate dengan program IBM SPSS 25 Edisi 9. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.

40. Ceci, L. (2023). Countries with the most TikTok users 2023. Retrieved May 25, 2023, from <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1299807/number-of-monthly-unique-tiktok-users/>

41. Tanyildizi, N. I., & Yolcu, A. S. (2020). The Use of Women Beauty as Advertising Attraction: Semiological Analysis of Three Magazine Advertising. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF HUMANITIES AND EDUCATION (IJHE), VI(13), 49-67.

APPENDIX I

Table 6. Operationalization of variable

Code	Item Measurements	Source
Customer Engagement		
CE1	I spend more time on men's grooming products TikTok shop that have an interesting host.	Wongkitrungrueng & Assarut (2018)
CE2	I would become a follower of a men's grooming products TikTok shop that use an interesting host on TikTok live streaming.	
CE3	I would certainly try to keep in track of the activity of men's grooming products TikTok shop that use interesting host on live streaming.	
CE4	I would certainly try to follow the activities of men's grooming products TikTok shop that employ interesting host on live streaming.	
CE5	I am certainly to recommend TikTok shop that use interesting host on live streaming.	
CE6	I encourage my friends and relatives to establish a business with men's grooming products TikTok shop that uses interesting host on live streaming shop.	
CE7	In the near future, I will definitely buy men's grooming products from interesting host on TikTok live streaming shop.	
Trust in Host		
TH1	I believe in the information that provided by interesting host of TikTok live streaming shop.	Wu & Huang (2022)
TH2	I can trust toward interesting hosts of TikTok live streaming.	Wongkitrungrueng & Assarut (2018)
TH3	I believe that hosts of TikTok shop who use live streaming are trustworthy.	
Visual Appearance		
VA1	The physical beauty of live streaming host arouses me.	Wongkitrungrueng & Assarut (2018)
VA2	The physical beauty of live streaming host stimulates me.	
VA3	Visual masculine or feminine appearance of host on men's grooming products TikTok shop will affect my trust, since the products itself has specific gender target market.	Tong et al (2022)
VA4	I will be more attracted toward specific style of host on watching TikTok shop for selling men's grooming product (I.e. only typical men's style/only typical women's style).	

Host Approach: Promotion		
HAP1	I found the men's grooming products TikTok host who tell the promotion was interesting.	Hou et al (2020)
HAP2	Host of TikTok on men's grooming product who tell the promotion was effective in gathering viewers.	
HAP3	I am able to gained the good price regarding the men's grooming product from host who tells the promotion.	
Host Approach: Humor		
HAH1	Hosts with humor approach on TikTok live streaming are interesting host.	Barta et al (2022)
HAH2	Host with humor approach on TikTok live streaming will give me pleasurable experience.	
HAH3	I would become a follower of a men's grooming products TikTok shop that use humor on TikTok live streaming.	
Interaction: Review the Product		
INR1	I feel host of men's grooming product who reviews the products on TikTok live streaming is interesting.	(Tong, et al., 2022) Hajli (2015)
INR2	I feel information from host of men's grooming product who reviews the products is reliable on TikTok live streaming shop.	
INR3	Generally, host of men's grooming product who reviews the products on TikTok live streaming is trustworthy.	
INR4	I found a men's grooming product that suits my preference after I asked the host on TikTok's live streaming.	
Interaction: Consultation		
INC1	I believe the host is willing to consult with me in live streaming.	Tong et al (2022)
INC2	The host made me feel she/he wanted to listen to the viewers.	
INC3	After consulting me for the product, I feel the host is interesting.	Wongkitrungrueng & Assarut (2018)